

Journal: <https://ifsmrc.org/index.php/aijrm>**MORPHOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF THE MOST ACTIVE ABBREVIATED UNITS IN GAMING CHATS****Mokhinur Murodova Azamat qizi**

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Abstract

The rapid development of digital communication has significantly influenced modern language use, especially in online gaming environments. This article investigates the morphological structure of the most frequently used abbreviated units in English gaming chats. The study is based on language samples collected from multiplayer games such as PUBG, Valorant, Dota 2, League of Legends, Call of Duty, Fortnite, and Discord gaming communities. The research applies descriptive, comparative, and morphological analysis methods. The findings demonstrate that initialisms, acronyms, clipping, blending, affixation, and semantic transformation are the dominant word-formation processes in gaming discourse.

Keywords: gaming chat, abbreviation, slang, lexical innovation, PUBG, morphology.

Annotatsiya

Raqamli kommunikatsiyaning jadal rivojlanishi zamonaviy til qo'llanilishiga, ayniqsa onlayn geyming muhitida sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilidagi geyming chatlarda eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan qisqartma birliklarining morfologik tuzilishi tadqiq etiladi. Tadqiqot PUBG, Valorant, Dota 2, League of Legends, Call of Duty, Fortnite hamda Discord geyming hamjamiyatlaridan to'plangan til namunalariga asoslanadi. Izlanishda tavsifiy, qiyosiy va morfologik tahlil usullaridan foydalanildi. Natijalar geyming diskursida initsializmlar, akronimlar, clipping, blending, affiksatsiya hamda semantik transformatsiya yetakchi so'z yasash jarayonlari ekanligini ko'rsatdi.

Kalit so'zlar: gaming chat, qisqartma, sleng, leksik innovatsiya, PUBG, morfologiya.

Аннотация

Стремительное развитие цифровой коммуникации оказало значительное влияние на современное употребление языка, особенно в среде онлайн-гейминга. В данной статье исследуется морфологическая структура наиболее часто употребляемых сокращённых единиц в англоязычных игровых чатах. Исследование основано на языковых материалах, собранных из многопользовательских игр, таких как PUBG, Valorant, Dota 2, League of Legends, Call of Duty, Fortnite, а также из игровых сообществ Discord. В работе применялись описательный, сравнительный и морфологический методы анализа. Результаты показывают,

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что инициализмы, акронимы, clipping, blending, аффиксация и семантическая трансформация являются ведущими способами словообразования в игровом дискурсе.

Ключевые слова: игровой чат, сокращение, сленг, лексическая инновация, PUBG, морфология.

Introduction

In the twenty-first century, online gaming has transformed from a recreational activity into a global communicative space where millions of users interact daily. Real-time communication in games requires speed, brevity, and efficiency. As a result, players frequently employ shortened lexical units, abbreviations, and slang expressions. Gaming chats differ from traditional written communication because messages are produced instantly active gameplay. Players must exchange tactical information, emotions, warnings, and reactions within seconds. Therefore, shortened forms such as b, c, k, sus, cul8r, urg8t, NP, IMHO, wp have become standard elements of gaming discourse. This article aims to analyze the morphological structure of the most active abbreviated units used in English gaming chats and identify the most productive word-formation patterns.

Literature Review

Digital discourse has attracted increasing attention in modern linguistics. According to David Crystal, the digital era has significantly accelerated language change, as new words, expressions, and patterns of usage now spread much more rapidly through the internet and social media. In particular, slang circulates faster than in previous generations because of constant online connectivity and instant communication [2, p.49]. The global expansion of digital media has greatly increased the influence of film-related slang, allowing informal expressions to move across languages and cultures more quickly than before. Streaming platforms such as Netflix, Amazon Prime Video, and Disney+ have helped popularize slang terms beyond their original cinematic contexts. Films also contribute to linguistic and cultural change, especially among younger audiences, as shown by the spread of expressions like sus (from suspicious) [4, p.259]. Gaming communication demonstrates rapid lexical innovation due to the need for immediate interaction. Previous studies have explored internet slang and online abbreviations; however, gaming chats remain relatively underexplored from a morphological perspective. This study seeks to fill that gap.

Methodology

The study uses qualitative and quantitative approaches. Language samples were collected from mainly gameplay recordings, Discord server, multiplayer matches from the following platforms: PUBG, Dota 2, CS2, Mobile Legends. More than 50 chat examples were observed, from which the most frequent abbreviated forms were selected for analysis.

Here you can see some examples of abbreviations which were taken from real online gaming:

twitch.tv/topson

In these 2 pictures, some abbreviations and slang units are written like: LIL, LOOL, KEKW, Tec, XDD, Wombo Combo. LIL-little, weak player; LOOL- laughing out loud (stronger laughter); KEKW- embarrassing, chaotic happens; Tec- technical; XDD- big smile, funny fails; Wombo Combo- coordinated combo attack where multiple abilities combine perfectly.

Twitch.tv/oilrats

Analysis and Discussion

1. Initialisms are formed from the first letters of multi-word expressions. Each letter is pronounced separately.

GG	Good game	Polite ending
AFK	Away From Keyboard	Temporarily absent
HP	Health Points	Player health
XP	Experience Points	Progress points

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DPS	Damage Per Second	Attack efficiency
MVP	Most Valuable Player	Best performer
FPS	Frames Per Second	Technical performance
BRB	Be Right Back	Temporary leave
WD	Well Done	Polite ending

2. Acronyms

LOL – Laughing Out Loud

YOLO – You Only Live Once

LFG – Looking For Group. These forms express emotion and social interaction. These expressions serve not only practical purposes but also create a sense of membership within online communities [3, p.212].

3. Clipping – They shorten longer words while preserving meaning. For example, *ultimate*; *mic- microphone*; *stats – statistics*; *app – application*; *champ – champion*. Clipping is highly productive because players prioritize speed. Shortening refers to the reduction of a word by removing one or more syllables while preserving its meaning. Common examples include *bro*, *sis*, *lang*. Clipping is a more specific type of reduction in which part of a word is omitted, producing forms such as *goin* for going, *talkin* for talking, *smilin* for smiling. These forms are especially common in informal online discourse where brevity is valued [5, p.230].

4. Blending – combines parts of two words:

Tryhard -try+hard

lagspike – lag+spike

ragequit – rage+quit

speedrun – speed+run. Blended forms often carry expressive meaning.

5. Affixation – some gaming terms develop through suffixes and prefixes like *troll- trolling*; *feed-feeder*; *camp -camper*; *buff -buffed*; *nerf- nerfed*. Suffixes such as *-er*, *-ing*, *-ed* remain productive in gaming vocabulary.

6. Semantic Shift and Slang Development – Some ordinary words gain specialized gaming meanings. Semantic change is central to gaming language evolution:

Word	Common Meaning	Gaming Meaning
Carry	Transport	Lead team to victory

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Feed	Give food	Die repeatedly helping enemy
Farm	Agriculture	Collect resources
Tank	Military Vehicle	Absorb damage
Bot	Robot	Weak AI or poor player

According to Baugh and Cable (2002), digital communication has significantly transformed written language by encouraging various forms of lexical reduction and informal expression. On social media platforms users frequently simplify words and phrases in order to communicate faster and efficiently. These include shortening, contractions, unconventional spellings, abbreviations, acronyms and emoticons. He also notes the widespread use of contractions and compressed spellings in internet language. Examples include *gd* for good, *nxt* for next, *abt* for about, and *tmrw* for tomorrow. Such forms reduce typing effort and reflect the fast-paced nature of online communication. In addition, unconventional spellings like *gud* for good, *plz* for please, and *thanx* for thanks demonstrate how users creatively modify standard orthography for convenience or stylistic effect [1, pp.142-156].

Conclusion

Gaming chats represent a dynamic linguistic environment where abbreviation and lexical innovation flourish. The most active morphological processes include initialism, clipping, blending, affixation and semantic shift. These forms emerge from the communicative demands of speed, efficiency, and group identity. English gaming discourse continues to influence global online communication, making gaming chats an important object of modern linguistic research.

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